

Experience in the Implementation of a Permanence Strategy in Virtual Training in Technology

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Abstract

In 2023, the National University of Colombia, in a groundbreaking collaboration with the District Agency for Higher Education, Science, and Technology, pioneered a virtual training program specifically tailored for adult high school graduates. This innovative program was structured around four distinct technical lines: UI/UX interface design, mobile application development, digital animation, and video game development. It offered both basic and intermediate levels of training, with each level encompassing approximately 280 hours of comprehensive learning. Different actions were implemented to mitigate attrition during training, resulting in a significant increase in permanence compared to typical levels of virtual learning. The strategy included a data analysis system to estimate each individual's dropout risk, weekly calls to possible dropouts referred by tutors, follow-up of individuals requesting support in psychological and academic aspects, consultations referring to the National University, and the health network. Additionally, direct communication was established with potential dropouts through withdrawal tickets and psychosocial accompaniment to support students in increasing motivation and reducing anxiety, depression, and stress. On the other hand, peer learning was included, consisting of a mentorship program that invited students; a sponsor plan was implemented that asked those who voluntarily wanted to share their knowledge with those who needed support in the most challenging subjects. Lastly, motivational messages were emailed to encourage students to complete the course. The program had three groups throughout the year with similar population characteristics. The attrition rates were 9,7% for group 1, 5% for group 2, and 7% for group 3. Typically, this type of training has a dropout rate of around 30%, so the implemented strategy significantly positively affected the students' permanence in the program

Keywords: virtual learning, data analysis, peer learning, digital skills.

1 Introduction

Virtual education, also known as online education or distance education, refers to the teaching modality that uses information and communication technologies (ICT) to facilitate learning outside the traditional classroom environment (Rawashdeh, AZ. *et al.*, 2021). This modality has experienced significant growth in recent decades, transforming how people access education (Haleem A. *et al.*, 2022). Virtual education has its roots in distance education, which dates back to the 19th century with the creation of correspondence programs. With the advancement of communication technologies, such as radio and television, distance education evolved and adopted new forms of teaching. Virtual education has become an effective and accessible educational modality for millions worldwide (Betts K. *et al.*, 2020).

Virtual education is characterized by using digital platforms and multimedia resources to teach classes, carry out educational activities, and evaluate student learning. Through these tools, students can access educational content, interact with their peers and teachers, and carry out learning activities flexibly adapted to their needs (García Aretio, L., 2001). Some of the advantages described of this type of education are access to education, which allows students to access it from anywhere, as long as they have access to the internet; removing geographical barriers, and facilitating access to education for people living in remote areas or with mobility difficulties (Becerra, G. E., 2017). Another advantage is the flexibility of schedules, which makes it easier for students to combine study with other responsibilities, such as work or family. Virtual education has allowed a

more excellent choice and variety of programs and courses previously unavailable in specific geographies (Sanabria Cárdenas, I., 2020). This will enable students to choose programs that best suit their interests and educational needs. In addition, there is a reduction in travel and accommodation expenses for students and academic institutions.

Despite its advantages, virtual education has some essential disadvantages; one of the main criticisms of virtual education is the lack of physical interaction between students and teachers. The absence of face-to-face contact can make it difficult to create social bonds and develop interpersonal communication skills. Likewise, virtual education requires a high degree of motivation and discipline on the part of students, as they do not have the direct supervision of a teacher (Aakash, A., 2022). Some students may struggle and need a set class schedule to stay motivated and organised.

For all of the above, virtual education currently faces several challenges, among which the following stand out: first, to guarantee the quality of distance education. Virtual programs and courses must meet the same quality standards as face-to-face programs, ensuring students acquire the knowledge and skills necessary for their training. Second, teachers' adaptation to new technologies and teaching methodologies. Therefore, teachers must receive adequate training and support to deliver classes effectively in virtual environments. Third, regardless of socioeconomic or geographical status, equitable access to virtual education is another major challenge. This involves ensuring everyone has access to the internet and the technological resources necessary to participate in virtual education (Meza Villares, E. & Soledispa Toala, F., 2023). Fourth, developing safe and efficient educational platforms to ensure virtual education's quality and security comply with data protection and privacy standards (Ruiz Salvador, L. & Álvarez Llerena, C., 2021). Finally, another significant challenge is to develop effective methods for assessing and certifying learning in virtual environments. Finding ways to evaluate student learning somewhat and objectively is critical to ensuring the validity and reliability of results (Azam, R. & Yousef, N., 2010). These challenges are related to the academic success of students and the dropout rate, which is usually higher in this modality than face-to-face training.

Several types of variables affect the dropout rate. Studies on the influence of socioeconomic variables on dropout can be grouped into two large groups: those in which no variable was related to dropout and those in which one or more related variables were found. Within the first group, the study carried out by Orellana *et al.*, 2020: a systematic review of the literature on student dropout in virtual higher education programs from 2004 to 2019, in which 52 variables related to dropout were found. However, none of them correspond to socioeconomic aspects. Within the second group, studies by (Barbosa-Camargo *et al.*, 2021 Guzmán Rincón *et al.*, 2021) have highlighted the role of the schooling of both parents or the mother since having parents with higher levels of education is negatively correlated with dropout. On the other hand, Palacio Sprocket *et al.*, 2020 indicate that students from lower-income families are at a disadvantage when entering higher education, given the social and cultural capital.

On the other hand, Soons *et al.* (2009 cited in Guzmán Rincón *et al.*, 2021) indicate that the student's perception of well-being mediates the relationship between income and dropout, the higher the income, the greater the perception of well-being and the decrease in the possibility of dropping out. Likewise, funding programs have been found to benefit retention in higher education students (Barbosa-Camargo *et al.*, 2021). Finally, regarding the trend in Latin America and the Caribbean, Munizaga Mellado *et al.* (2018) report that in the studies carried out in these areas from 1990 to 2016, the most frequently found variables include financing, income, and, again, educational level of parents (21%).

Gender has been a variable present in different studies on attrition. However, the results have been contradictory. Barbosa-Camargo *et al.* (2021) found that being a woman had a negative correlation with

dropout; likewise, Orellana *et al.* (2020) in their systematic review of causes of dropout in virtual environments. However, in other studies, such as that of Olarte Moyano (2020) carried out in a technical institution in Colombia, gender did not show a significant relationship with dropout. On the other hand, age is an individual variable that affects dropout. In the systematic review carried out by Orellana *et al.* (2020), it was found that the older the age, the greater the probability of dropout, especially between the ages of 29 and 35; this finding is supported by other studies reported by Guzmán Rincón *et al.* (2021), although they report that this variable is related to others, especially with work and family obligations, since they compete in time availability with academic work.

Academic performance is related to dropout in two ways: the first refers to accumulated academic capital, and the second to program performance. Students with lower academic capital have a higher risk of dropping out, given the academic demands of higher education (Guzmán Rincón *et al.*, 2021); this finding has been replicated in studies conducted in Colombia (Barbosa-Camargo *et al.*, 2021) and Chile (Guzmán Rincón *et al.*, 2021). Especially in virtual environments, other relevant variables are evidenced, such as time management techniques, educational skills, preparation for self-directed learning, self-efficacy, procrastination, and academic experience (Orellana *et al.*, 2020) On the other hand, performance within the program is also related to dropout, the better the performance, the lower the probability of dropping out in both face-to-face and virtual environments (Guzmán Rincón *et al.*, 2021; Orellana *et al.*, 2020).

Program quality is related to dropout through variables such as (1) teacher-student interaction; the more significant the interaction, the greater the probability of remaining in a virtual program until completion (Stanford-Bowers, 2008, cited by Orellana *et al.*, 2020; Guzmán Rincón *et al.*, 2021), (2) student-to-student interaction, program design can increase student-to-student interaction and thereby increase student engagement and academic performance; and finally (3) the number of students per teacher (Guzmán Rincón *et al.*, 2021). On the other hand, the institution's support variable is also related to dropout; the lower the accompaniment of students through the well-being division, the higher the dropout rate, especially in private institutions (Guzmán Rincón *et al.*, 2021).

During 2023, the Faculty of Engineering of the National University of Colombia trained more than 5000 students in Bogota over 18 years of age, allowing them to strengthen IT competencies and 4.0 skills, contributing to the reduction of the digital divide. To execute the Todos a la U program, the University implemented pedagogical processes and methodologies of challenge-based learning in a hybrid training modality to seek alternatives for learning and interaction between students, mentors, and tutors through virtuality assisted by technological means and face-to-face. The following diplomas were taught: Mobile Application Development, Video Game Development, Digital Animation Design, and UX/UI User Interface Design. Each of the diplomas taught was carried out at two levels, basic and intermediate: Basic level: understood as the initial level of each training programme, Intermediate level: understood as the complementary level of each IT industry skills training program.

This paper presents the experience of implementing a dropout reduction strategy in a virtual IT training program developed by the National University of Colombia and the Atenea (Spanish initials for *Agencia Distrital para la Educación Superior, la Ciencia y la Tecnología*).

2 Permanence Strategy in Virtual Training

Atenea's student retention strategy focuses on providing vital support that allows students to achieve their academic goals and actively participate in the courses they enrol in. This strategy is committed to offering

resources and services specifically designed to address students' individual needs, thereby fostering their academic success and commitment to their education.

In three cohorts, different actions were implemented to mitigate dropout, which had a significant impact and were established as follows: Psychosocial Accompaniment, in which greater motivation and reduction of anxiety, depression, and stress were achieved, which were the leading causes of registration on the button. He was also able to provide an immediate response to a case of suicidal ideation.

The second action consisted of supporting students with low academic performance through a program called "sponsor plan," where students generated a greater understanding of the subjects; the third strategy was based on internal monitoring tools to support student retention. Therefore, it was essential to make weekly calls to possible dropouts referred by tutors and/ or trainers and for absences, in which the primary needs of the students were identified. Subsequently, the respective support was suggested.

Likewise, possible dropouts referred through withdrawal tickets and follow-up to people with special conditions were retained, where any doubts or concerns regarding the course were resolved. Finally, in the fourth action, students were encouraged to complete the program with Motivational Messages and levelling successfully.

2.1 Information Sources

In order to establish the appropriate strategies for the beneficiaries, a characterization survey was carried out, asking about socioeconomic level, level of education, belonging to an ethnic group, and whether or not they had any particular condition (visual, physical, mental, language, developmental, etc.). This information generated an exhaustive accompaniment for people who mention some type of difficulty, whether technical, personal, or family. Similarly, greater motivation and retention were established with calls, forms, assistance, and information from tutors, trainers, and the support and help desk team.

The implementation of the Virtual Campus brings a wave of excitement. The online learning platform is not just a technological advancement, but a gateway to a comprehensive, high-quality virtual environment for our participants.

The Virtual Campus is fully operational and accessible to users, becoming the central axis of the training experience. Through this platform, students will be able to access interactive educational content, participate in discussion forums, interact with instructors and peers, and take full advantage of the learning opportunities offered by the program.

Alongside the Virtual Campus, we've made significant strides in improving the unaltodosalau.com Help Desk. The interfaces have been redesigned with user-friendliness in mind, making it a breeze to create and track tickets. We've also integrated a dedicated space for instructional videos, addressing user feedback and providing visual guides for key processes.

The launch of the Virtual Campus and the improvements to the Help Desk reflect Todos a la U's commitment to providing a quality learning experience and exceptional technical support to its participants. These initiatives strengthen the virtual educational environment, promote equitable access to training opportunities, and provide the necessary tools for students' academic success.

2.2 Deployed Actions

During the training process, different strategies were implemented to mitigate dropout, which had a significant impact. Some of them were:

2.2.1 Sponsor Plan

This plan was open to the voluntary participation of those students who demonstrated a greater understanding of the topics so that through study spaces on the platform, they could share their knowledge and learning with students who reported low academic performance or meager attendance and/or participation in the program. This way, a link of accompaniment between students was generated, and peer support was promoted to help students understand and comprehend academic activities and progress the training process.

2.2.2 Psychosocial support

A space for care and support was set up on the training platform with the support of the psychosocial support team. Virtual sessions were held with students who requested it. In these meetings, students were motivated and sought to support the reduction of anxiety, depression, and stress (the main causes of student registration). On the other hand, in order to offer students input to reflect on their progress in the training program and generate motivation to continue in the process, the psychosocial support team made contact by telephone and/or email with participants at risk of dropping out and who reported a shallow level of progress or engagement with the program.

2.2.3 Accompaniment to students identified as at higher risk of dropping out

Dropout risk criteria and tools were established to identify and accompany students in this condition. Among the criteria were students with special conditions, with the highest number of fouls that they referred to as some difficulty, who requested tutoring, and who had meager participation during the training progress. Among the detection strategies was a data analytics tool and the support of the team of trainers/tutors. Tutorials were given, communications were advanced, and tickets were created to support them.

2.2.4 Other strategies

Other strategies implemented were related to the retention of withdrawal requests, the accompaniment of people who referred some difficulty through a technical help desk, the accompaniment in the uploading of documents at the beginning of the call, and the follow-up of particular cases (suicidal ideation and learning difficulties).

3 Results

3.1 Cohort 1

A total of 4069 students were enrolled in cohort 1, distributed in eight diploma courses, each with an intensity of 280 hours. 52% (n=2107) obtained a certificate of approval, 19% (n=769) obtained a certificate of attendance, 20% (n=797) failed the diploma course, and 9.7% (n=396) dropped out of the diploma course. The basic level had a dropout rate of 9.4% (n=380), while the intermediate level reported 5.3% (n=16), which could indicate that preliminary knowledge of the subject generates a more excellent permanence in training. Regarding age, the population with the highest dropout rate was in the 18 to 20 age range, with 13.3% (n=110). The number of children of the participants generated a slight difference in the academic result, with the lowest dropout rate among those who had a child at the time of training, with 8.6% (n=54). On the other hand, the stratum had a counterintuitive behaviour; the lowest dropout rate was in stratum one (1) and the highest in stratum four (4).

3.2 Cohort 2

The behaviour of cohort 2 was more optimistic; out of a total of 1617 students enrolled in four basic level diploma courses each, with an intensity of 280 hours each, 76% (n=1234) obtained a certificate of approval, 4% (n=62) obtained a certificate of attendance, 15% (n=240) failed the diploma course and 5% (n=81) dropped out of the diploma course. The topic with the highest attrition was UX/UI interface design, with 8.6% (n=28), while mobile app development had 2.9% (n=16). No significant differences were found in age or number of children for this group.

3.3 Cohort 3

The last cohort consisted of 500 students who completed the basic level of Cohort 1 and continued their studies at an intermediate level. Five hundred students (500) were divided into four intermediate-level diploma courses, each with an intensity of 280 hours. 82% (n=411) obtained a certificate of approval, 5% (n=23) obtained a certificate of attendance, 6% (n=30) failed the diploma course, and 7% (n=36) dropped out of the diploma course. In this case, the topic with the highest attrition was video game development, with 10.3% (n=7), and the lowest was UX/UI interfaces, with 5.2% (n=6). It is worth mentioning that in none of the cohorts were differences by genre observed.

4 Conclusions

The virtual training program implemented by the National University of Colombia (UNAL) in collaboration with the District Agency for Higher Education (Atenea) significantly impacted ("Todos a La U") the provision of accessible technical training to adult high school graduates in Bogotá.

By deploying a comprehensive student retention strategy focused on data analysis, peer mentoring, psychosocial support, and proactive communication, the program achieved much lower dropout rates (5-9.7%) than the typical 30% attrition in virtual learning environments.

Over 5,000 students were trained across three cohorts in areas such as UI/UX design, mobile app development, digital animation, and video game development. The strategies allowed many of these students to successfully complete the intensive 280-hour basic and intermediate-level programs.

The experience demonstrates the potential of virtual education to provide scalable technical upskilling opportunities, especially when coupled with robust student support mechanisms tailored to the challenges of the online learning format.

From now on, the lessons learned from this initiative can help inform best practices for designing and delivering effective virtual training programs that minimize dropout risks. If replicated across other domains, the strategies used can contribute to bridging digital skill gaps and providing accessible education at scale.

Additionally, the data on factors influencing retention rates in a virtual setting can guide further research into improving online pedagogical models, support interventions, and learning technologies to enhance virtual education outcomes.

Overall, this work highlights a promising approach to leverage the accessibility of virtual learning to impart in-demand technology skills to diverse populations while ensuring high completion rates through a comprehensive student support ecosystem.

The National University of Colombia's virtual training initiative successfully reduced high attrition rates. This was achieved through a comprehensive approach that included data-driven intervention, peer mentorship, psychosocial support, and active communications.

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